

Representation Of Africans As Degenerate People in Joseph Conrad's Heart Of Darkness

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 01, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Representation, Orient, Degenerate, Uncivilized, Orientalism, Africa</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4906260</p>	<p><i>The paper aims to analyze the stereotypical representation of Africans in Joseph Conrad's Heart of Darkness (1899). The selected text is analyzed in light of the various stereotypes described by Edward Said in his famous work Orientalism (1979). These stereotypes define the Orient as timeless, degenerate, strange, inferior and feminine. Conrad represents the Africans as backward and degenerate people who are uncivilized in nature. The text was analyzed from a postcolonial angle. To analyze the selected text, postcolonial theory has been used as a theoretical framework that is based on Said's concept of 'Self' and 'Other'. Said informs in Orientalism (1979) that the West has based its knowledge on the stereotypical representation of non-Europeans in its literature that is replete with the mythical constructions about such non-European nations as Africa is one in this particular study. The textual analysis technique was used to understand the hidden meanings in the text under study. Close reading of the novel shows that Conrad has represented the Africans as uncivilized and degenerate people living in the 'dark continent'.</i></p>

Introduction

The research study contains an intensive analysis of Joseph Conrad's *Heart of Darkness* that portrays the Africans as degenerate people to perpetuate the prevalent notion propagated by the European writers in their works about the Eastern nations. The study indicates the mythical construction in the Western literature that the European nations are superior to the non-European nations. These non-European nations are portrayed as inferior 'Others' in European texts. To dismantle such a mythical construction propagated by the Orientalists, Said (1979) has formulated in his *Orientalism* a popular concept of 'Self' and 'Other', which is often used as a useful tool to dissect and critically evaluate the European canonical texts that are meant to establish the superiority of the West and inferiority of the East, the terms that carry the connotations of 'Self' and 'Other', respectively, in colonial discourse. This type of literature represents the non-Europeans as "under humanized, antidemocratic, backward, and barbaric" (Said, 1979, p. 150). On the basis of such negative assumptions, such nations are deemed as weak and feminine enough to establish their existence practically. Such a phenomenon corresponds to the most popular words of Karl Marx, "They cannot represent themselves; they must be represented" (Said, 1979, p. xii). Said elaborates it further that "representations are formations" and takes the opinion of Roland Barthes that the operations of language are named as deformations. In this context, the West is seen to be involved in form and deforming the image of the Orient due to its peculiar sensitivity for a specific piece of land that is known as "the East" (p. 273). In this regard, it becomes extremely important that denotative and connotative meanings of this word 'representation' should be properly evaluated with reference to two standard dictionaries that have defined it in different ways. Representation, as defined in Oxford dictionary as "the description or portrayal of someone or something in a particular way" (Web, 2021). Similarly, representation is defined in Cambridge dictionary as, "the way that someone or something is shown or described" (Web, 2021). The former definition refers to 'the description and portrayal', and the latter emphasizes the description of 'someone or something'. Hence, representation may be understood to be a field that primarily indicates to the way people or places defined, depicted and portrayed in various works of art as 'Other'.

Problem Statement

European novelists have often depicted the non-European people as pathetic and degenerate in nature, who, because of their coloured complexion, are unable to govern their own affairs. By inventing different types of stereotypes in literary texts, these European writers make a ground to justify their occupation of distant territories in the world. Such a stereotypical representation of the non-Europeans nations has often been the area of interest for colonial writers in literary texts. In light of such a theoretical representation of the colonized as inferior 'Others', this research paper aims to investigate how Joseph Conrad has represented the African natives in a canonical English novel *Heart of Darkness*. The study analyses the selected text from a postcolonial perspective.

Literature Review

Richardson (2000), referring to the term representation, stated that Said has discussed 'representation' in a more general context in his *Orientalism* (1979), which is characterized by the concepts and assumptions of the Western writers about the 'Near East'. Such concepts and assumptions, Richardson referred to, are to be analyzed so as to understand the mode of representation of the non-European nations that reside in the European consciousness as inferior 'Other'. In this regard, Said (1979) says that scholars who write, teaches, or execute research about the Orient, whether they are sociologists, anthropologists, philologists or historians are the Orientalists and what they person do is 'Orientalism'.

Colonial literature has almost five hundred years history. Initially, it was rooted in the European mercantile expansion towards different parts of the world, but with the passage of time it is formulated as a discourse in terms of stories and descriptions about the non-European lands. Boehmer (2005) says that colonial discourse is profoundly entrenched in Colonial Literature as well as the literary works of the Colonialists. This type of a literature is comprised of the colonial experiences and perceptions, that is composed in metropolitans in the time of colonization of different regions, it contains works of British writers during the colonial period, for instance, novels of Dickens and travelogues written by Trollope are seen to be the popular works that underpin the image of Britain as a powerful state in the world. Whereas, literature of the colonialists, records the colonial expansion and it exemplifies the stance of the imperialists. It propagated the image of European culture as superior to the rest of other cultures on the globe. It uses a language fully characterized by different types of stereotypes so as to intercede the relationships between the colonizers and the colonized (Boehmer, 2005). In this connection, Boehmer further states that "the history of the world for the past few centuries has been profoundly shaped by colonial interests, then there is a sense in which much of the literature produced during that time can be said to be colonial or postcolonial" (p. 1).

Said (1979) defines the Orient to be a place where the West has its richest, biggest and oldest colonies that happen to be the main source of civilization as well as languages for the West and also grows to be its cultural contestant "and one of its deepest and most recurring images of the Other. In addition, the Orient has helped to define Europe (or the West)" (Said, 1979, p. 1). Boehmer (2005) states, "The characterization of colonized people as secondary, abject, weak, feminine, and other to Europe, and in particular to England, was standard in British colonialist writing" (p. 77). Thus, it seems that the Western novelists remained quite eager to explore the peculiar characteristics of the Orient. European writers have often labelled the land of the colonized nations as a mysterious territory that is to be explored. Such a mysterious land has captivated the mind of many intellectuals both spiritually and materialistically (Ibrahim, 2013).

It is an essential question to identify the reason that why these European writers go to the territories of the Orient and to further view the historical context of colonization critically and its association with the European inhabitants, or as Fredric Jameson (1981) stated that a political perspective of literary texts should not be kept aside because it is "the absolute horizon of all reading and all interpretation" (p. 1).

Western novelists played a very significant role in paving the way for the colonizers to colonize the people of a distant territory through their literary writings that are political in nature. It is an attempt by Orientalists to monopolize the discourse on non-Western societies and perpetuate their own paradigms of the 'Other' (Mazrui, 2005, p. 79), by articulating their own experiences and also their individual fantasies and imaginations irrespective of the real social reality exists on the ground. In this connection, Bozdogan (1988) argued that a few of the artists remained inclined to enframe the Orient by labelling them with singular forms and shapes so as to make them a plain object of depiction. Bozdogan further elaborates that such type of portrayal is found in close proximity to nature that is "systematically discovered, studied, and abstracted . . . so is the Orient explored, recorded, and illustrated through the meditation of representation . . . thereby the Orient is set-up in such a way that it represents itself as representable" (p. 39). There are writers who portray the Orient in their texts as savage, uncivilized and barbaric implicating the position that the "accuracy of representational techniques is thus employed to construct an image . . . may or may not be faithful to the actual experience" (Bozdogan, 1988, p. 42).

The discourse in Orientalism, McLeod (2000), makes use of peculiar stereotypes and constructs particular images attributed to the Orient by employing inert and negative terms so as to establish the myth about the Orient to be static in nature. In the similar fashion, they make efforts to develop a view that they are much concerned with the Orient and work with sincerity to civilize them and provide them with a good sense about life by bring them into the ambit of developed culture of Europe. It is deemed to be apparently a justified and legal stance on part of the Europeans to civilize the Orient.

Joseph Conrad's place in English literature as a great writer of fiction is unquestionable. Leavis (1973), considers Conrad to be among the writers identified with the 'Great Tradition' of English literature. He is known to be a novelist who has broadened the canvas of the novel writing by making ample space for exploration and examining human experiences. Daiches (1962) endorses such an opinion by further confirming the various technical features of multiple voices used in the novels by Conrad. Guerard (1978) further critically analyses *Heart of Darkness* in a similar vein but also characterizes it in a specific mode, when he argues that it is "among

the half-dozen greatest short novels in the English language" (p. 9). Such commendable words prove him to a dedicated critic of Conrad. Similarly, Leavis (1973), who is known for his rigorous and censorious critical views, stated that "*Heart of Darkness* is, by common consent, one of Conrad's best things" (p.174). Chinua Achebe (1988), a well-known African novelist, termed Conrad to be "a great stylist of modern fiction" (p.2), but, at the same time, also relentlessly criticized *Heart of Darkness* that it "eliminates the African as human factor and parades in the most vulgar fashion, prejudices and insults from which a section of mankind has suffered untold agonies" (Achebe, 1988, p.10).

Methodological Framework

This research study is qualitative. The selected text has been analyzed by employing descriptive, analytical and interpretivist approach. The text has been minutely examined and interpreted from a postcolonial perspective. Said's (1979) concepts of 'Self' and 'Other' have been thoroughly exploited from various angles in order to understand the nature of representation of the Africans as degenerate nation in the selected text. Close reading of the text has been very much useful in investigating the hidden colonial connotations in the novel.

Discussion and Analysis

The novelist at the very onset in *Heart of Darkness* presents the African land to be a place that has ominous characteristics. The narrator in the novel describes the deteriorating traits of the place of the upper reaches towards the West in concrete terms "farther west, on the upper reaches the place of the monstrous town was still marked ominously on the sky, a brooding gloom in sunshine, a lurid glare under the stars" (Conrad, 1902, p. 7). Marlow (the narrator) endorses it at once by stating that it "has been one of the dark places of the earth" (Conrad, 1902, p. 7).

Marlow, while romanticizing the accomplishments of the Europeans in the Africa region in past, gives a possible description about the feelings of a commander posted in Africa. To Marlow, this was a great achievement of the commander who was brave enough to be spending his time in such a degenerate atmosphere. He continues with his words about the commander been in the region "the very end of the world", that he would be walking up the river that was characterized by "sandbanks, marshes, forests, savages---precious little to eat fit for a civilized man" (Conrad, 1902, p. 9). In this description, African land is portrayed to be a strange and alien place that is characterized by "a sea the colour of lead" and "a sky the colour of smoke" (Conrad, 1902, p. 9). It is a common way of describing the colonized land (Africa in this case) in a language replete with degenerate elements. Such a description of Africa exactly corresponds to the description of Henry Richardson regarding Australia in *The Fortunes of Richard Mahony* "as harsh, shabby, and ugly, an inhospitable world for its eponymous Irish hero who never ceases to feel himself an exile" (Innes, 2007, p. 80). In these words, the land of Australia is described to be a futile and unnecessary part of nature, as Marlow has described Africa where everything is degenerate in nature. The place is marked as unsuitable for civilized people rather such a piece of land is only meant for the people who are uncivilized.

Conrad portrays the land of Africa as wild in all respects, which absorbed the entire military camp that was stationed over there "like a needle in a bundle of hay--cold, fog, tempests, disease, exile, and death--death skulking in the air, in the water, in the bush. They must have been dying like flies here" (Conrad, 1912, p. 9). Literary writing, in which a character is deprived of the elements of voice and agency, "set in Africa, or 'the East', or other areas colonized by European powers, belongs to a long history of representation of these areas as uncivilized, inhabited by inferior peoples – if inhabited at all – and in need of 'development'" (Innes, 2007, p. 42). These words refer to the underlying connotations in such text that tries to establish that it is very much difficult for the Europeans to stay in Africa because they are "men enough to face the darkness" of "sandbanks, marshes, forests, savages---precious little to eat fit for a civilized man" (Conrad, 1902, p. 9). He also mentions a young person who travels to the place to make his fortunes, but where "utter savagery, had closed round him--all that mysterious life of the wilderness that stirs in the forest, in the jungles, in the hearts of wild men" (Conrad, 1902, p. 9). The young man who is desirous of making his good fortunes on this land would get nothing as "there's no initiation either into such mysteries. He has to live in the midst of the incomprehensible, which is also detestable" (Conrad, 1902, p. 9). The degenerate features associated with the land help the European writers to portray the inhabitants of the land degenerate too, such a description of places and the people living there gives a strong justification to the colonizers to come and invade the distant territories in the world in the name of giving civilization to these so-called 'degenerate natives'.

Africa is depicted to be an empty place on the globe and that is to be explored in order to make it place suitable for the foreigners to come and inhabit it and give it a civilizing seeds. This type of exploratory motives pave a way for all the European explorers to come and occupy this land. Marlow, in the novel, articulates his childhood experience when he would be searching places on maps, and in that he would see South America, Africa, and Australia places good for exploration. Said (1993) terms it 'Western imperialist illusions' vis-a-vis the Third World regions that are thought to "have no life, history, or culture to speak of, no independence or integrity worth representing without the West. And when there is something to be described it is, following Conrad, unutterably corrupt, degenerate, irredeemable" (p. xxi). Africa is identified to be a blank spot on the globe, which Marlow thinks to be a piece of land that is to be explored. But, as he is grown-up, this place is not a

blank place for him anymore because there are rivers and lakes "it had ceased to be a blank space of delightful mystery--and had become a place of darkness" (Conrad, 1902, p. 12). Further, the land is termed to be an infertile place, which is unproductive in nature. This land is characterized by mysterious attributes. It is also characterized by some malignant influences. All things are referred in vague terms, i.e., using names of hazardous insects and animals so as to identify the place with animal kingdom. Marlow's description of the river that he finds on the map resembles to a big uncoiled snake which head is in the sea and its curved body expanded to a vast land and its tail engrossed in the bottomless resorts of the land, that fascinated him "as a snake would a bird", that had also captivated him (Conrad, 1902, p. 12). The writer employs concrete imagery in order to create a magical impact of the scene in a way that would produce an evil charm in description that will be a total deception for the people located at a distance. This type of distorted description of Africa alludes to the biased motives and understanding of the European colonizers about this territory, which they subjugate and rule.

The natives of African are portrayed as some strange creatures who are wild like fierce animals and are controlled through chains in their necks. Marlow's description clearly portrays them as degenerate in body appearance, "I could see every rib, the joints of their limbs were like knots in a rope; each had an iron collar on his neck, and all were connected with a chain whose bights swung between them rhythmically clinking", which he terms "ominous voice" (Conrad, 1902, p. 22). This description of the native Africans is very much explicit in this scene of the novel in which portrayal of the natives resembles some weird type of creature. The chains in their necks tell that they are dangerous and wild beasts that are to be controlled by force who if freed might do a great harm to the civilized people around. The words 'chain', 'rope', and 'iron collar' in these lines are used to certify the notion that these natives are to be civilized through ruthless and stiff ways. These words symbolically allude to the power strategies employed to manage the wild natives. Marlow continues that "they were called criminals" with "their meagre breasts panted together the violently dilated nostrils quivered, the eyes stared stonily uphill" (Conrad, 1902, pp. 22-23). These natives were identified as criminals without doing any crime. It is one of the many colonial machinations employed by the colonial novelist in their works to justify their subjugation of the non-Europeans on the pretext that they enter the land with the civilizing mission. The description of the African natives in the above lines clearly reflect them as lifeless objects that walk like robots with no sign of any human expression on their faces. These natives are like the animals whose fierce nostrils are open and their stony eyes resemble the wild animals, which due to some luggage on their backs move slowly in a fixed direction. The description shows them as tamed creatures that do not move even their eyeballs and breathe fast with their open nostrils, passing Marlow "within six inches, without a glance, with that complete, deathlike indifference of unhappy savages" (Conrad, 1902, p. 23).

Marlow, when going towards Kurtz's station along with his company men, comes in confrontation with the natives who attack them. The natives with Marlow are cannibals who live on human flesh that is why in the middle of the fight, their headman approaches Marlow and shows his cannibal instinct when he tells Marlow that would catch the men from the other tribesmen so as to eat them. This Marlow describes in the text "Their headman, a young broad-chested black,... with fierce nostrils...stood near me" (Conrad, 1902, p. 58). Their headman says "catch 'im" and "snapped, with a bloodshot widening of his eyes and a flash of sharp teeth--catch 'im. Give 'im to us" (Conrad, 1902, p. 58). Here, Marlow asks him the reason "what would you do with them?" he replies "Eat im!" (Conrad, 1902, p. 58). The scene clearly aims to establish that the native people were cannibals who would consume the human flesh as food of other natives. Putting in other words, they would use "rotten hippo-meat" which these natives had brought with them to eat on the steamboat, this meal equals flesh of human beings. Marlow describes the wretched condition of the land inhabited by the people (natives) "You can't breathe dead hippo waking, sleeping, and eating, and at the same time keep your precarious grip on existence" (Conrad, 1902, p. 58).

Conclusion

Conrad has portrayed the natives in Africa as degenerate people who are not only degenerate in appearance but also in their living practices. Such portrayal of the natives in the novel helps the European explorers to pave the way for subjugation of African land and also to occupy their natural resources. These natives are termed as uncivilized and uncultured people and who are characterized by cannibalism because they consume the flesh of other human fellows as their meal. Conrad tells the world that Africa is a land that is occupied by degenerate population that is far away from the light of civilization, so it becomes the duty of the civilized West to go and occupy the land. This all is suggested in the name of civilizing mission of the natives. That is why Africa is shown to be a land stagnant in nature where food items stink like stagnant water and that could only be consumed by degenerate people who are already there.

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